

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Acetaldehyde by Cerium (IV) Salts

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The kinetics of the oxidation of acetaldehyde by two different ceric salts, e.g., ceric sulphate and ceric perchlorate have been studied at different temperatures.

Shorter¹ has studied the oxidation of acetaldehyde and also other aldehydes with ceric sulphate at 70° with an idea to see the effect of substituents. In the present investigation, the oxidation of acetaldehyde by ceric sulphate and ceric perchlorate has been studied at different temperatures and activation energies have been calculated. In addition the effect of the addition of salts and the variation of H⁺ ion concentration has been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Acetaldehyde solution (Naarden variety) was purified by distillation and estimated by the usual procedure. Other reagents, used were of the highest purity available. The details of ceric ammonium sulphate and ceric perchlorate have been described in our previous communication^{2,3}. Sulphates of sodium and magnesium were of E. Merck G. R. quality. Sodium perchlorate was prepared by the neutralisation of Na₂CO₃ with HClO₄.

To determine the amount of ceric ion reduced per mole of acetaldehyde, a known amount of the aldehyde was mixed with large excess of ceric perchlorate and kept for 2-3 days. After that period ceric ion was estimated by the usual procedure from which the amount of ceric ion reduced per mole of acetaldehyde has been calculated. 1 mole of acetaldehyde requires 3.98 equivalents of ceric ion at 25°. The products of oxidation have been found to be CH₃COOH and HCOOH and confirmed by usual tests. One mole of acetaldehyde, on oxidation, produces 0.97 mole of formic acid as estimated by permanganate.

To determine the formation of formic acid at any time, acetaldehyde and ceric solution were mixed and aliquot parts were withdrawn at suitable intervals and poured into an excess alkali. The precipitated ceric hydroxide was separated by filtration and washed thoroughly with water. The filtrate was acidified with H₂SO₄ and distilled. The distillate collected at 100-101° was estimated with standard permanganate. This method of separation of formic acid from acetaldehyde was tested by taking mixture of solutions of formic acid and acetaldehyde and estimating formic acid which agreed with the amount taken within ±2%. The spectrophotometric technique used in kinetic runs, has been described in previous communication³.

1. J. Shorter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3425.

2. K. K. SenGupta and S. Aditya, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1963, **38**, 25.

3. K. K. SenGupta and S. Aditya, *J. Electrochem. Soc. (Japan)*, 1964, **32**, 200,

The oxidation of acetaldehyde has been studied in the presence of excess ceric ions following the consumption of oxidant with time. The plot of $\log \frac{(O.D.)_0}{(O.D.)_t}$ vs time gives a straight line indicating that the reaction (the consumption of ceric) is unimolecular. The velocity constants have been calculated from the slopes of the $\log \frac{(O.D.)_0}{(O.D.)_t}$ vs 't' plot. A typical plot has been shown in the figure 1.

FIG 1. OXIDATION OF ACETALDEHYDE BY Ce^{IV} PERCHLORATE.

Effect of H^+ ion on the reaction velocity: The reaction velocities were measured at different hydrogen ion concentrations. The concentrations of hydrogen ions were varied by the addition of sulphuric and perchloric acid. It has been found that hydrogen ion accelerates the rate of oxidation of acetaldehyde and the plot of K against h_0 (Hammett acidity) shows a straight line (Fig. 2).

FIG 2 INFLUENCE OF ACIDITY ON RATE CONSTANT

Effect of salts on the reaction velocity: Three different salts such as NaClO_4 , Na_2SO_4 and MgSO_4 were used during the oxidation of acetaldehyde by ceric sulphate and only NaClO_4 in the case of oxidation by ceric perchlorate. No salt effect is observed in sodium perchlorate solution. Na_2SO_4 and MgSO_4 retard the rate of reaction. The results have been summarised in the tables II and IV.

TABLE I

$(\text{CH}_3\text{CHO}) = 0.00815M$; (Ceric Sulphate) = $0.0252M$ Temp. = 22° ; $\lambda = 420 \text{ m}\mu$.

No.	H_2SO_4 molarity	(Hammett acidity)	$K \times 10^2 (\text{min}^{-1})$
1	1.125	1.74	1.266
2	0.920	1.23	0.856
3	0.650	0.77	0.575
4	0.560	0.65	0.460

TABLE II

$(\text{CH}_3\text{CHO}) = 0.00815M$; (Ceric Sulphate) = $0.0252M$; Temp. = 25° ,
 $(\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4) = 0.710M$, $\lambda = 420 \text{ m}\mu$.

No.	Salt and its concentration	$K \times 10^2 (\text{min}^{-1})$
1	0	0.9212
2	$M \text{ NaClO}_4$	0.9212
3	$M \text{ MgSO}_4$	0.8160
4	$M \text{ Na}_2\text{SO}_4$	0.6909

Effect of temperature on reaction velocity: The reaction velocities have been calculated at three different temperatures. All the three experiments were performed at identical H^+ ion concentration. The results have been plotted in the Fig. 3. From the $\log K$ vs $1/T$ plot, the activation energy has been calculated. The activation energies are found to be 18.3 ± 0.9 and 6.0 ± 0.3 K. cal in the cases of ceric sulphate and ceric perchlorate respectively.

FIGURE - 3

Rate of formation of formic acid: The formic acid formed at different times has been estimated following the technique described in the experimental section. The curve in Figure 4 shows a mean curve of the duplicate runs. The ceric ions consumed at various times in these experiments have also been estimated. From the amount of ceric ion consumed and the amount of formic acid formed, the amount of acetic acid has been calculated on the assumption that the amount of ceric in excess of the stoichiometric requirement of formic acid, produces acetic acid. The experimental results (mean) and also the calculated figures for acetic acid are recorded in table V. A comparison of column '2' and '4' shows that molar concentration of formic acid is nearly twice that of acetic acid. 3.98 moles of ceric consumed per mole of acetaldehyde would yield 0.5 mole of acetic acid and one mole of formic acid. The results show that the stoichiometry is approximately constant throughout the course of oxidation.

FIG 4. OXIDATION OF ACETALDEHYDE BY CERIC SULPHATE.

TABLE III

$(\text{CH}_3\text{CHO}) = 0.00815M$; (Ceric Perchlorate) = $0.0234M$;
Temp. = 22° , $\lambda = 420 \text{ m}\mu$.

No.	HClO_4 in molarity	(Hammett acidity)	$K \times 10^2 \text{ (min}^{-1}\text{)}$
1	1.451	2.96	1.130
2	1.348	2.50	1.790
3	1.321	2.38	1.727

TABLE IV

$(\text{CH}_3\text{CHO}) = 0.00815M$; (Ceric Perchlorate) = $0.0234 M$,
Temp. = 25° , $\lambda = 420 \text{ m}\mu$, $(\text{HClO}_4) = 1.40 M$

No.	Salt and its concentration	$K \times 10^2 \text{ (min}^{-1}\text{)}$
1		2.533
2	$M \text{ NaClO}_4$	2.533

It is quite interesting to note that $\log (\text{HCOOH})$ against time is linear (Figure 5.) The plot of $\log (\text{CH}_3\text{COOH})$ against time is also linear. Such first order rate dependence is expected on the basis of the mechanism that the free radicals formed attain a steady concentration and the final product is formed as a result of reaction between the free radical and ceric ion.

TABLE V

Concentration of formic acid and acetic acid (calculated) formed by oxidation of CH_3CHO with ceric sulphate on the basis of smoothed curve from two sets of oxidation runs.

$(\text{CH}_3\text{CHO}) = 0.08M$, (Ceric Sulphate) = $0.025 M$, Temp. = 25° ,
 $(\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4) = 1.14 M$.

Time in minutes	$[\text{HCOOH}]$ formed in molarity	$[\text{Ceric}]$ consumed in molarity	$[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}]$ calculated in molarity
3	0.0022	0.00909	0.0012
4	0.0026	0.0098	0.0014
6	0.0032	0.0130	0.0017
8	0.00375	0.0152	0.0020
9	0.00405	0.0164	0.0021
10	0.00430	0.0175	0.0023
12	0.0048	0.01919	0.0023

FIG.5. OXIDATION OF ACETALDEHYDE BY CERIC SULPHATE.

DISCUSSION

It has already been mentioned that 3.98 moles of ceric ion consumed per mole of acetaldehyde in the oxidation process. The products of oxidation are formic acid and acetic acid.

As suggested by Shorter and Hinshelwood⁴, the oxidation takes place according to the reaction :

and steps (i) and (ii) taking place in 50% and 50%, account for the stoichiometric of 3.98. They have followed the oxidation at 70° and report that 5.75 equivalents of ceric ion are used up per mole of acetaldehyde and accounts for the stoichiometry on the basis

4. J. Shorter and C. N. Hinshelwood, *J. Chem., Soc.*, 1950, 3276.

that (i) is 90% and (ii) is 10%. In explaining the mechanism, they suggest that the reaction (i) is through the enolic form. Presumably the reaction (ii) is from keto form of the aldehyde. Now the keto-enol equilibrium is temperature dependent. This is possibly the reason for the difference in the amount of ceric ion consumed per mole of the substrate. No comparison could be made as there are no data in the literature giving the variation of the keto-enol equilibrium of acetaldehyde with temperature.

Regarding the oxidation of the enolic form, i.e., step (i), Hinshelwood and Shorter⁴ have suggested the following steps:

They did not say anything about the step (ii). It is suggested that the reaction possibly proceeds through the hydrated form of acetaldehyde in the manner indicated:

The oxidation of acetaldehyde is acid catalysed. Similar observation has been made by Hinshelwood and Shorter⁴. In the present case, oxidation has been followed with ceric sulphate and ceric perchlorate; the acidity being controlled by sulphuric acid and perchloric acid. By way of correlating the oxidation rate with acidity it has been found that rate constant with both sulphate and perchlorate against h_0 , the Hammett acidity (fig. 2) gives a straight line. The slope is slightly less than unity.

On the basis of Zucker-Hammett hypothesis^{5,6}, one might feel tempted to infer that the solvent molecule does not take part in the transition but it is perhaps better to be satisfied with the correlation without an attempt to theorise.

Coming to the effect of salt on the oxidation, no change in the rate constant in the presence of sodium perchlorate indicates that the reaction is not ionic. The retardation by sulphate is due to its concentration with ceric ion to form different complexes as suggested by different authors^{7,9}. In connection with the oxidation of hypophosphorus acid by Ce(IV) ion, Mishra and Gupta¹⁰ also reported similar observation, where H^+ ions increase

5. F. A. Long and M. A. Paul, *Chem. Rev.*, 1957, **57**, 935.
6. R. L. Moore and R. C. Anderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 167.
7. T. N. Bondereva and V. F. Barkovskii, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1965, **10**, 127.
8. S. K. Mishra and K. K. Gupta, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 1943.
9. T. J. Hardwick and E. Robertson, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1951, **29**, 828.
10. R. P. Bell, (Proton in Chemistry), (1959)

the rate but sulphate ions decrease it. It is interesting to mention that like acetaldehyde, hypophosphorus acid is also said to exist in two forms, e.g., normal and active forms which are tautomers.

The authors wish to thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, India, for financial assistance.

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Received, October 23, 1967.